

RELaTED, A FLEXIBLE APPROACH TO THE DEPLOYMENT AND CONVERSION OF DH NETWORKS TO LOW TEMPERATURE, WITH INCREASED USE OF LOCAL SOLAR SYSTEMS

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The RElated concept

- Ultra-Low Temperature (ULT) System ($\sim 45^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- Decentralized DH network
- Buildings acting as energy nodes
- Substations allow for bi-directional heat exchange
- Incorporation of low-grade heat sources
- Heat Pumps recover heat from cooling applications (air conditioning, ventilation, supermarket cooling, etc.).
- Decentralized, Building Integrated Solar Thermal

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Expected development

RELaTED will be demonstrated in 4 selected locations:

- Green field development in VINGE, DK
- DH network with large share of biomass in TARTU, EE
- Large DH network with incorporation of large RES resources in BELGRADE, SR
- Corporate DH network in IURRETA, ES

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Project partners: TECNALIA, Danish Technical Institute, Fortum Tartu, Beogradske Elektrane, Basque Government, Metro Therm, Nibe, Aventa, Industrias IMAR, Basque Energy Agency, Mazovia Energy Agency, Institute of Baltic Studies, FEDARENE, El Taller De Comunicación y CIA.

<http://www.relatedproject.eu/>

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